

Facile synthesis of Ru^{II} Schiff base complexes : Spectral characterization and antimicrobial applications

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Abstract : Diamagnetic ruthenium(II) complexes of the type [RuCl(CO)(pyridine)(L)] (where L = monobasic tridentate Schiff base ligands) were synthesized by the reactions of Schiff bases derived from the reactions of *o*-aminobenzoic acid and Knoevenagel condensate of β -ketoesters and appropriate ruthenium metal precursor [RuHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₂(py)]. Elemental analyses and spectral (FT-IR, UV-Vis and ¹H, ³¹P NMR) studies of all the new synthesized complexes suggest the presence of an octahedral environment around the Ru^{II} ion. Cyclic voltammograms of all the complexes display oxidation and reduction potentials. Superoxide dismutase activity (SOD) of these complexes has also been examined. These complexes were also subjected to study their biocidal activity against *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Botrytis cinerea* and *Aspergillus niger*.

Keywords : Ruthenium(II), Schiff base, cyclic voltammogram, biocidal, SOD.

Introduction

Schiff base ligands are considered as privileged ligands because they can be easily prepared by the condensation between aldehydes and amines¹. Tetradentate Schiff base ligands are able to coordinate with many different metal ions forming stable compounds and some of these complexes are recognized as oxygen carriers^{2,3}. Schiff base complexes of transition metals having O and N donor atoms have shown an exponential increase in inorganic catalysts for various organic transformations⁴⁻⁶. Among the second row transition metal ions, ruthenium mediated oxidations are finding application due to the unique properties of this extremely versatile transition metal whose oxidation state can vary from -II to +VIII⁷⁻¹⁰. A large number of Schiff bases and their complexes have significant interest and attention because of their biological activity including anti-tumour, antibacterial, fungicidal and anti-carcinogenic properties^{11,12}. The main aim of the production and synthesis of any antimicrobial compound is to inhibit the causal microbe without any side effects on the patients. In addition, it is worthy to stress here on the basic idea of applying any chemotherapeutic agent which depends essentially on the specific control of only

one biological function and not multiple ones. The chemotherapeutic agent affecting only one function has a highly sounding application in the field of treatment by anticancer, since most anticancers used in the present time affect both cancerous diseased cells and healthy ones which in turns affect the general health of the patients. Therefore, there is a real need for having a chemotherapeutic agent which controls only one function. In this paper, we discuss the synthesis, spectral characterization, catalytic and biocidal efficiency of ruthenium(II) Schiff base complexes. Schiff base ligands were synthesized from the reactions of *o*-aminobenzoic acid with Knoevenagel condensate of β -ketoesters¹⁵ (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Physical measurements :

All the reagents used were of analaR or chemically pure grade. Solvents were purified and dried according to standard procedures. RuCl₃.3H₂O purchased from Loba Chemie was used without further purification. The starting complexes [RuHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₃]¹⁶ and [RuHCl(CO)(B)(PPh₃)₂] (B = pyridine)¹⁷ were prepared according to the literature procedures and the Schiff bases were

Ligands	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
HL ¹	H	CH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅
HL ²	C ₄ H ₄	CH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅

Scheme 1. Synthesis of new Schiff base ligands.

derived by condensing *o*-aminobenzic acid with Knoevenagel condensate of β -ketoesters. Catalytic superoxide dismutase¹⁸ and biocidal¹⁹ studies were carried out according to reported procedures. The micro analyses were performed using Vario EL III CHNS analyzer at Cochin University, Kerala, India. IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ using Shimadzu instrument. ¹H and ³¹P NMR spectra for the ligands were recorded in Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore. Electronic spectra were recorded in CH₂Cl₂ with a Systronics Double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer-2202 in the range 200–800 nm. Electrochemical studies were recorded in dichloromethane solution using a glassy carbon working electrode and [NBu₄]ClO₄ was used as supporting electrolyte. Melting points were recorded on a Veego VMP-DS melting point apparatus and are uncorrected.

Recommended procedures :

Synthesis of new Schiff base ligands :

Tridentate Schiff base ligands (Scheme 1) were synthesized from the reactions of *o*-aminobenzic acid with

Knoevenagel condensate of β -ketoesters¹⁵ 2-[1-ethyl-2-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)-3-oxo-butylideneamino]-benzoic acid and 2-[2-ethoxycarbonyl-3-(3-hydroxynaphthalen-2-yl)-1-methyl-allylideneamino]-benzoic acid) in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanolic medium and refluxed for 6 h and their purity was checked by thin-layer chromatography.

Synthesis of new Ru^{II} Schiff base complexes :

To a solution of [RuHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₂(py)] (0.1 g, 0.1 mmol) in benzene (20 cm³) the respective Schiff base ligands (0.03–0.05 g, 0.1 mmol) were added in 1 : 1 ratio (Scheme 2). The mixture was then heated under reflux for 6 h. The resulting solution was concentrated to ca. 3 cm³ and the product was separated by the addition of the small amount of light petroleum (60–80 °C). It was filtered and recrystallised from CH₂Cl₂/light petroleum (60–80 °C) and dried in vacuum (yields 70–83%).

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity :

In vitro SOD activity was measured using alkaline DMSO as a source of superoxide radical ion (O₂^{•-}) and nitrobluetetrazolium (NBT) as O₂^{•-} scavenger¹⁸. In general, 400 mL of the sample to be assayed was added to a

Scheme 2. Synthesis of ruthenium(II) Schiff base complexes.

solution containing 2.1 mL of 0.2 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.8) and 1 mL of 56 MM NBT. The tubes were kept in ice for 20 min and then 1.5 mL of alkaline DMSO solution was added while stirring. The absorbance was then monitored at 540 nm against a sample prepared under similar condition except that NaOH was absent in DMSO. The % inhibition (η) of NBT reduction was calculated using following equation :

$$(\% \text{ Inhibition of NBT reduction}) = (1 - k'/k) \times 100$$

where, k' and k represent the slopes of the straight line of absorbance values as a function of time in presence and in absence of SOD mimic or a model compound, respectively. IC₅₀ value of the complex was determined by plotting the graph of percentage inhibition.

Results and discussion

The new complexes are soluble in most of the common organic solvents. Their purity was checked by thin-layer chromatography. The analytical data obtained for all the new complexes agree well with the proposed molecular formulae (Scheme 2) and are listed in Table 1. In all the complexes Schiff bases behave as mono basic tridentate ligands.

Spectroscopic studies :

Infrared spectral analysis :

The IR spectra of the ligands were compared with those of the ruthenium complexes in order to confirm the binding mode of the Schiff base ligands to ruthenium ion

in the complexes are listed in Table 2. For the anthranilic acid moiety, the ν_{OH} absorption observed at 3300 cm⁻¹ in the free Schiff base and the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ frequency of the carbonyl was seen as a band at 1680 cm⁻¹. In the complexes the bands were observed in the 1642–1645 cm⁻¹ and 1434–1439 cm⁻¹ regions arising from asymmetric (ν_{asyCOO^-}) and symmetric (ν_{symCOO^-}) stretching of the carboxylato group^{13,14,22}. This indicates the coordination of the carboxyl group to the ruthenium metal ion in the complexes. The differences between the asymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies of the coordinated carboxyl group lie in the 226–208 cm⁻¹ range, a clear indication of the monodentate coordination of the carboxyl group with the free carbonyl group^{13,14,20}. In the free ligands the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ bands appears in the region of 1608–1610 cm⁻¹. In all the complexes, the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band is shifted to lower frequency in the range 1586–1596 cm⁻¹, indicating coordination of the Schiff bases through the azomethine nitrogen atom^{13,14,21,22}. In the free ligands, the carbonyl stretching frequency of the ester group was found in the range of 1718–1719 cm⁻¹. On complexation these bands shifted to a higher frequency in the range of 1750–1751 cm⁻¹²³, which indicates the coordination through the carbonyl group in the ester. In the entire complexes strong band appears in the region 1925–1958 cm⁻¹ owing to terminal carbonyl group. In the complexes, a medium intensity band is observed in the 1020 cm⁻¹ region characteristic of the coordinated pyridine^{24,25}. There is no band observed for Ru-H, which indicates the

Table 1. Analytical data of Ru^{II} Schiff base complexes

Complexes	Colour	Melting point (°C)	Emperical formula	Molecular weight	Elemental analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)		
					C	H	N
HL ¹	Yellow	118	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ NO ₅	353.37	67.98 (67.80)	5.42 (5.40)	3.96 (3.91)
HL ²	Brown	105	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ NO ₅	403.43	71.45 (71.40)	5.25 (5.21)	3.47 (3.43)
[Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L ¹]	Brown	193	RuC ₂₆ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₆ P	595.99	52.40 (52.38)	3.89 (3.85)	4.70 (4.68)
[Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L ²]	Brown	220	RuC ₃₀ H ₂₆ ClN ₂ O ₆ P	647.06	55.69 (55.62)	4.05 (4.03)	4.33 (4.31)

Table 2. FT-IR spectral and UV-Vis data of new Ru^{II} Schiff base complexes

Complexes	IR spectra (cm ⁻¹)					UV-Vis λ_{max} (nm)
	$\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO}^-)$	$\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO}^-)$	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	Ester $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	
HL ¹	1665	1462	1610	1719	–	262, 299, 368, 401, 420, 472, 635
HL ²	1657	1465	1608	1718	–	261, 299, 388, 370
[Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L ¹]	1645	1439	1596	1750	1925	251, 300, 368, 396, 446
[Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L ²]	1642	1434	1586	1751	1958	251, 304, 366, 402, 431, 468, 494, 597

elimination of hydride ion from the ruthenium metal startings. The band appears around 3233–3334 cm^{-1} in the ligands due to phenolic OH. On complexation bands for phenolic OH appears in the complexes also, this indicates the non involvement of phenolic OH group in coordination to the ruthenium atom.

Electronic spectral analysis :

Electronic spectra of all the ligands and complexes recorded in dichloromethane showed four to eight bands in the region 262–635 nm (Table 2). For the ligands, the high intensity bands around 262–388 nm and 401–635 nm has been designated as $n-\pi^*$ and $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions respectively for the electrons localized on the C=O, C=N and COOH group of the Schiff bases. All the complexes are diamagnetic, indicating the presence of ruthenium in the +2 oxidation state. The ground state of ruthenium(II) in an octahedral environment is $^1A_{1g}$, arising from the t_{2g}^6 configuration. The excited state terms are $^3T_{1g}$, $^3T_{2g}$, $^1T_{1g}$ and $^1T_{2g}$. Hence four bands corresponding to the transition $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ are possible in order of increasing energy. The electronic spectral bands at around 597 nm are assigned to $d-d$ transitions. The other high intensity band in the visible region around 251–494 nm has been assigned to charge transfer transitions arising from the metal t_{2g} level to the unfilled π^* molecular orbital of the ligand^{26–30}. The pattern of the electronic spectra for all the complexes indicate the presence of an octahedral environment around the ruthenium(II) ion similar to that of other ruthenium octahedral complexes^{26–31}.

^1H and ^{31}P NMR spectroscopic analysis :

The ^1H NMR spectra of the ligands were recorded in chloroform (Table 3). Multiplets are observed around 6.4–8.0 ppm in all the ligands have been assigned to aromatic protons. For COOH and phenolic OH protons in all the

ligands showed a singlet in the region 13.0–13.8 ppm and 9.8–11.0 ppm, respectively. For CH protons all the ligands show singlet in the region 4.8–5.8 ppm. For ethoxy group methylene and methyl protons shows quartet and triplet in the region 3.1–4.7 ppm and 2.1–3.6 ppm, respectively. Methyl protons appear as a singlet in the region 1.2–2.5 ppm.

The ^1H NMR spectra of all the complexes were recorded to confirm the binding of Schiff bases to the ruthenium ion (Table 3). A representative spectrum of the complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)\text{L}^1]$ is shown in the Fig. 1. A sharp singlet observed in the region 10.5–12.0 ppm for phenolic OH protons for all the ligands. This indicates the non involvement of phenolic OH group in coordination. Multiplets are observed around 6.2–8.4 ppm in all the complexes have been assigned to aromatic protons of triphenylphosphine, pyridine and Schiff base ligands^{32,33}. All the complexes showed singlet in the region 2.8–5.2 ppm for CH protons. Methyl protons appear as singlet in the region 0.9–2.5 ppm for the ligands HL₁ and HL₂. For ethoxy group, the signal for methylene and methyl protons appears as a quartet and triplet in the region 2.2–3.9 ppm and 1.2–3.1 ppm, respectively in the complexes. A sharp singlet observed for COOH protons for all the ligands in the region 13.0–13.8 ppm was disappeared in all the complexes³⁴. There is no peak observed in the negative region which indicates the absence of hydride ion in all the complexes.

To confirm whether the triphenylphosphine group or heterocyclic nitrogen base is present in the complexes, the ^{31}P NMR spectra were recorded for the complexes, which exhibits no such signal, confirming the absence of the triphenylphosphine group. This result indicates the retention of coordinated pyridine in the new complexes even after the coordination of tridentate Schiff bases²⁷.

Table 3. ^1H NMR spectral data of Ru^{II} Schiff base complexes

Complexes	^1H NMR (ppm)
HL ¹	3.1–3.7 (q, CH ₂), 2.1–2.5 (t, CH ₃), 1.2 (s, CH ₃), 6.5–8.0 (m, aromatic), 11 (s, Ph-OH), 13.0 (s, COOH), 5.8 (s, CH)
HL ²	4.2–4.7 (q, CH ₂), 3.2–3.6 (t, CH ₃), 2.5 (s, CH ₃), 6.4–8.0 (m, aromatic), 9.8 (s, Ph-OH), 13.8 (s, COOH), 4.8 (s, CH)
$[\text{Ru}(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{py})\text{L}^1]$	0.9 (s, CH ₃), 2.7–3.0 (q, CH ₂), 1.2–1.7 (t, CH ₃), 3.4 (s, CH), 6.2–8.0 (m, aromatic), 11.0 (s, Ph-OH)
$[\text{Ru}(\text{Cl})(\text{CO})(\text{py})\text{L}^2]$	1.6 (s, CH ₃), 2.8–3.1 (q, CH ₂), 2.1–2.4 (t, CH ₃), 3.7 (s, CH), 6.8–8.0 (m, aromatic), 11.3 (s, Ph-OH)

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectrum of HL³ Schiff base ligand.

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectrum of complex [Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L¹].

Cyclic voltammetry :

Cyclic voltammetric studies were performed for all the complexes at a glassy-carbon working electrode in dichloromethane solution (Table 5, Fig. 4). The oxidation and reduction of each complex were characterized

by well defined waves with $E_{1/2}$ values in the range from 0.87 to 0.97 mV (oxidation) and -1.04 mV (reduction) against Ag/AgCl electrode. Complexes showed redox couples with peak to peak separation values (ΔE_p) ranging from 396 to 916 mV revealing that this process is at

Table 4. Electrochemical data of new Ru^{II} Schiff base complexes

Complexes	Ru ^{III} -Ru ^{II}				Ru ^{II} -Ru ^I			
	E_{pa} (V)	E_{pc} (V)	$E_{1/2}$ (V)	ΔE_p (mV)	E_{pa} (V)	E_{pc} (V)	$E_{1/2}$ (V)	ΔE_p (mV)
[Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L ¹]	1.428	0.512	0.97	916	-1.242	-0.846	-1.04	396
[Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L ²]	1.149	0.589	0.87	560	-	-	-	-

Supporting electrolyte : [NBu₄]ClO₄ (0.1 M); scan rate, 0.1 mV s⁻¹; reference electrode, Ag-AgCl.
 $\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$; $E_{1/2} = 0.5 (E_{pa} + E_{pc})$, where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are the anodic and cathodic peak potentials in volts, respectively.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of complex [Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L¹].

Table 5. Biological activity of Ru^{II} Schiff base complexes

Complexes	Antibacterial activity						Antifungal activity					
	<i>S. epidermidis</i>			<i>E. coli</i>			<i>B. cinerea</i>			<i>A. niger</i>		
	0.25	0.5	1	0.25	0.5	1	0.25	0.5	1	0.25	0.5	1
[Ru(H)(Cl)(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂ (py)]	19	19	19	15	16	16	19	21	21	16	16	16
HL ¹	5	6	6	5	5	6	6	7	6	5	8	6
HL ²	8	8	9	7	7	8	9	8	9	6	8	8
[Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L ¹]	19	21	21	17	19	19	19	21	22	21	21	29
[Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L ²]	17	17	18	21	22	22	20	21	21	22	22	22
Standard	23	22	19	21								
Dichloromethane	No activity						No activity					

Staphylococcus epidermidis, *Escherichia coli*, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Aspergillus niger*.

best quasi-reversible. This is attributed to slow electron transfer and adsorption of the complex on to the electrode surface. The complex [Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L¹] showed only oxidation potential^{26,35}.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) mimic activities :

The SOD activities of complexes were investigated by NBT assay method. In the present study, we have prepared two ruthenium(II) complexes. Among the two com-

plexes, [Ru(Cl)(CO)(py)L²] complex showed better SOD activity than other complexes. Fig. 4 represents the plot of percentage of inhibiting NBT reduction with an increase in the concentration of complexes. The ruthenium(II) complexes showed SOD-like activity which was evaluated by the scavenger concentration causes 50% inhibition in the detector formation, IC₅₀. The observed findings indicate that the superoxide scavenging properties and oxidative behavior of the complexes were identical.

Fig. 4. Plot of percentage of inhibiting NBT reduction with an increase in the concentration of complexes.

Biocidal activities :

By testing the antibacterial and antifungal activity of these compounds we used more than one test organism to increase the chance of detecting antibiotic principles in tested materials. The sensitivity of a microorganisms to standard antibiotic, free Schiff base ligands and ruthenium(II) Schiff base complexes was determined by the assay plates which incubated at 28 °C for two days for fungus and at 37 °C for one day for bacteria. All of the tested compounds showed a remarkable biological activity against bacteria (*S. epidermis* and *E. coli*) and fungus (*Botrytis cinerea* and *Aspergillus niger*) by Disc diffusion method at 0.25%, 0.50% and 1% concentration and the results are shown in Table 5. The results indicate that the some of the ruthenium(II) Schiff base complexes show greater microbial activity when compared with parent ligands, ruthenium(II) precursors and standard refer-

ence (Ciprofloxacin and Co-trimoxazole) against same microbes under identical experimental conditions. It is known that the membrane of fungus and bacteria are surrounded by an outer membrane containing lipopolysaccharides. The newly synthesized Schiff bases and its ruthenium complexes seem to be able to combine with the lipophilic layer in order to enhance the membrane permeability of bacteria and fungus. The lipid membrane surrounding the cell favors the passage of only lipidsoluble materials; thus the lipophilicity is an important factor that controls the antimicrobial activity. Also the increase in lipophilicity enhances the penetration of Schiff base and its ruthenium(II) complexes into the lipid membranes and thus restricts further growth of the organism^{40,41}. The Schiff base and its ruthenium(II) complexes could enhance the antimicrobial effect on both strains probably due to >C=N, -COO-, CH₃ and phenyl groups, which interact with the double membrane. This would suggest that the chelation could facilitate the ability of a complex to cross a cell membrane^{37,43,43} and can be explained by Tweedy's chelation theory^{44,45}. Chelation considerably reduces the polarity of the metal ion because of partial sharing of its positive charge with donor groups and possible π -electron delocalization within the whole chelate ring. Also chelation increases lipophilic nature of the central metal atom, which subsequently favours its permeation through the lipid layer of the cell membrane⁴⁶. The variation in the effectiveness of different compounds against different organisms depends either on the impermeability of the cells of the microbes or on differences in ribosome of microbial cells. The microbial screening was repeated twice and the error limit was found to be 0.2–0.5 mm. The ruthenium(II) Schiff base complexes in the literature have shown poor antibacterial activities. But our complexes have shown better inhibitory activity against the bacteria and fungi than the standard compounds^{38,39,42}. Most of the complexes show better efficiency when compared with the standard (Ciprofloxacin and Co-trimoxazole).

An octahedral structure has been tentatively proposed for the new ruthenium(II) Schiff base complexes based on the analytical and spectroscopic data (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. General structure of new ruthenium(II) Schiff base complexes.

Conclusion

Ruthenium(II) Schiff base complexes of the type $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{L})]$ (where L = monobasic tridentate Schiff base ligands) were synthesized. The new complexes were characterized by elemental analyses, spectral (FT-IR, ^1H , ^{31}P NMR and UV-Vis) and cyclic voltammetric studies. Based on the analytical and spectroscopic studies, an octahedral geometry has been tentatively proposed for all the ruthenium(II) complexes (Scheme 3). These complexes were also subjected to find out their biocidal activity against *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Botrytis cinerea* and *Aspergillus niger*. Some of the complexes show higher activity than the standard bactericide and fungicide (Ciprofloxacin and Co-trimoxazole). The complexes show better SOD activity. On comparing with the previous literatures, our Schiff base complexes shows better activity in catalysis and biocidal studies^{47,48}. In this work, we preferred oxygen as the oxidant which is a greener technique.

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